

Patterns of genetic variation in the common starling,
Sturnus vulgaris, in South Africa

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Report for the Master Degree

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September 2011

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Acknowledgements

Je veux tout d'abord remercier Cécile. Merci de m'avoir accepté comme stagiaire, merci de m'avoir si bien encadré. J'ai beaucoup appris à tes côtés et cela n'a pas de prix.

Next I want to say thank you to Bettine and all my friends in the EGG lab: Nidia, Gayle, Lee, Rina, Danny, Dan, Minette, Sara, Ethel, Nina...

A special thank you to my fabulous flatmates Louise and Joanie who permit me to really appreciate the amazing South Africa!

Obviously thank you to my GGB friends, thank you to Mr Sarr and Mr Robert to offer me this great opportunity.

And a last thank you to my family and my friends in France who never forgot me and were always with me in South Africa.

Abstract

Exotic species are non-native plants or animals that are introduced into areas where they do not naturally occur. Exotic species can out-compete natives by reproducing faster, competing for food and habitat more efficiently, and thrive in the absence of natural predators, and therefore widely expand their distribution range. In such cases, exotic species become invasive and can represent a major threat to global biodiversity, human health and lead to economic losses. South Africa has been subjected to many exotic introductions, some of which have established and become invasive such as the common starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*). Less than 20 individuals, native from the United Kingdom, were introduced to South Africa in the 1890s. One century later, it has become invasive and it is found along the South African West and East Coast from Cape Town to Port Elizabeth. The objective of this study is to understand the population structure and dynamics in order to understand birds' dispersal and spread; two very important points for management and pest control. We sampled common starlings across their distribution in South Africa, and analysed them using microsatellite and mitochondrial data. For comparative purposes, we also included material from Namibia and the United Kingdom. In this study, we differentiate the native population (England) from the introduced population (South Africa-Namibia). Within the introduced range, the observed heterozygosity is of 0.613 compared to 0.698 for the native English population. Genetic differentiation ($F_{ST} > 0.032$) between native and introduced has been observed, however no structure in sub-population within the South African population was highlighted. Within the South African population, the genetic similarity between individuals decrease with geographic distance, indicating an isolation-by-distance pattern. The mean average squared of parent-offspring distance (σ^2) was estimate to varying between 2 and 10 km². Combination of microsatellites, mitochondrial data and GIS analysis permit to identified short and long distance dispersion in starling populations.

Introduction

a. Biological invasions

Human trade routes around the world have introduced alien species (e.g. species living outside its native habitat) in many countries. Introductions of exotic species can be intentional like for European rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) in Australia in 1859 or unintentional like for Asian predatory wasp (*Vespa velutina*) in 2004 in France (Williams and Moore 1989, Villemant *et al.* 2006). In most of cases, intentional introductions of exotic species are for agricultural, horticulture, forestry, biological control or pet trade. Sometimes, introduced alien species become invasive (Blackburn *et al.* 2011). The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) defined an alien invasive species as: “an exotic species which becomes established in natural or semi-natural ecosystems or habitat, acts as an agent of change, and threatens native biological diversity” (IUCN 2000). More precisely biological invasions are defined as the introduction, establishment, and spread of species outside their native range (Richardson and Pyšek 2006, Blackburn *et al.* 2011). In 2005, the Millennium Ecosystems Assessment wrote that invasive alien species is one of the most important direct drivers of change in ecosystems (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment 2005). In fact invasive exotic species can cause disappearance of some native species by competition for food, nest sites or habitat (Parker *et al.* 1999, Sakai *et al.* 2001). In addition, these species have no or fewer predators to regulate their population growth. All of these parameters support the fact that invasive species often threaten the ecosystems of their new habitat.

Published studies showed that invasive alien species follow a specific pattern of invasion (Kolar and Lodge 2001, Lodge *et al.* 2006, Blackburn *et al.* 2009, see also Figure 1 in Blackburn *et al.* 2011). In short, the first step is the introduction of alien species into a new habitat (Fig. 1). Then, there is the establishment of the exotic population which is followed by its spread. The final step is the ecological, human health or economic impact (Lodge *et al.* 2006).

Figure 1 : Schematic representation of the invasion pathway, the transitions in the process of a human-caused invasion (Lodge *et al.* 2006, Blackburn *et al.* 2009, Blackburn *et al.* 2011)

The problem posed by alien invasive species is international and concerned animals and plants well as microorganisms and viruses. However, when exotic species became invasive (one out of ever 1000 of them (Williamson and Fitter 1996)) it is a problem for ecologist but also for politics. In the USA (United States of America) alien invasive species cost 120 billion\$ in control, eradication and survey per year (Pimentel *et al.* 2005). Invasive species is an economic problem which cannot be ignored by politics and economists. In this context, national governments realized the

importance of gathering information related to invasive species, and active efforts to combat their spread. As such, funding was provided at national level to establish organizations such as the National Institute of Invasive Species Science (2005, USA), Invasive Species Research Institute (2008, Canada), Working for Water (1995, South Africa), Centre of Excellence for Invasion Biology (2004, South Africa).

Studies on successful invaders provide important keys for understanding the processes which will lead to invasion by an established alien species. Key questions are: from where did the alien species come? Where has it been introduced? How many times and how many individuals (i.e. propagule pressure)? What is the dispersal pattern and spread rate? Is the introduced population functioning as a metapopulation or as isolated subpopulations? Answers to these questions are essential for management and pest control.

b. Key points in invasion processes

Life history traits are important for the successful establishment and spread of an introduced species. In 2006, Facon *et al.* (2006) have highlighted that processes of bio-invasion are a combination of migration rate, environmental and evolutionary changes (e.g. genetics and life history traits). Thompson (1991) explained that asexual reproduction or autogamy is a key advantage for invasion success because of reproductive assurance of the small initial populations (Thompson 1991). However, these reproductive systems restrict the generation of new genetic variants. Lodge (1993) explained that invaders are often *r* strategists because of their great capacities of reproduction and dispersion (Lodge 1993). But Byers (2000) highlighted that as well, high competitive ability (i.e. *k* strategy) appears to be important (Byers 2000).

Capacity of dispersion is an important point to study. In fact understanding the dispersal pattern of invasion permits us to model and predict how the species evolve across its new habitat. These kinds of results could lead to a management program for the invasive species. Several models of dispersion exist (see also Wilson *et al.* 2009); the first was introduced by Sewall Wright and is named the island model. Its

idea is all sub-populations or demes exchanged genes independently to the geographic distance (Wright 1930, 1937). Later, another model named the stepping stone model keep the idea of the island model but limits gene migration to neighbouring sub-populations/demes (Kimura and Weiss 1964). This model is more realistic in the idea that in numerous species, individual dispersal is restricted in space. This means that there is a higher probability that individuals mate with individuals born in close proximity to themselves than individuals born far away. Between these two models, there is the isolation by distance model (IBD) where the main idea of this pattern is that the genetic differentiation increase with geographic distance. This model was tested in numerous case, for example to highlighted the history of post-glacial colonization of Europe by *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Sharbel *et al.* 2000), or to conservation of forest skinks in Australia (Sumner *et al.* 2001) or for studying the biology of cane toad an invasive species in Australia (Leblois *et al.* 2000).

In addition to the capacity of dispersal, other parameters such as number of competitors, environment or propagule pressure have been proved to play a primary role in invasion (Lockwood *et al.* 2005, Sax *et al.* 2005, Sax *et al.* 2007, Blackburn *et al.* 2009). Propagule pressure can be divided into two components: propagule size and propagule event. Propagule size refers to the amount of individuals introduced while propagule events would be the number of introduction events. It has been demonstrated that these two parameters are very important in order to mitigate Allee effect (i.e. small population density effect) for the survival of the introduced population (Lockwood *et al.* 2005). This propagule pressure will not only have a density effect, but it will also interact at the genetic level. Indeed, this founding effect by few individuals will induce a decrease of genetic diversity and thus allelic richness. This loss will be accentuated through generations by inbreeding and genetic drift due to the small population size. Genetic diversity is associated with capacity of adaptation (Frankham *et al.* 2009). Therefore genetic diversity is important in order to estimate the adaptive ability of the invasive population/species. While one single introduction event will lead to low genetic diversity, multiple introductions from multiples source

populations may increase evolutionary potential and allow for rapid evolution and geographic spread in the new environment. Therefore it is important to know the history of introduction. Bottleneck intensity will influence the genetic pattern of the invasive species. In fact England *et al.* (2003) have demonstrated that the probability of retaining allelic diversity is lower in severe than in disperse bottleneck population. Effects of these bottlenecks on genetic diversity were evaluated using microsatellite markers on *Drosophila* populations. Bottlenecks substantially reduced allelic diversity, heterozygosity and changed allele frequency distributions. Allelic diversity, scaled by heterozygosity, was lower in the intense than the diffuse treatments (England *et al.* 2003). A single introduction event can be expected to be similar to an intense treatment, while multiple introductions would mimic a diffuse treatment. In fact one species which have been introduced many times will not have the same genetic pattern than one which has been introduced only once. Thus we can distinguish few patterns of introduction.

When only one introduction occurred, it is highly probable that all individuals came from the same native population. This case is illustrated for example by the potato tuber moth (*Tecia solanivora*) which is an agricultural pest in South America and in Canary Islands. This insect has been introduced once to Venezuela inducing a strong initial genetic bottleneck and therefore reduced the number of introduced haplotypes. But despite this loss of genetic diversity, *Tecia solanivora* is the most successful invasive agricultural pests across the Northern Andean region (Puillandre *et al.* 2008). Potential explanations for this success would be its high reproductive rates. Another unexpected explanation is found in a very fortunate bottleneck effect by purging deleterious alleles that cause inbreeding depression (Frankham 2005). Similar positive effects have been found in the Argentine ant (*Linepithema humile*). Tsutsui *et al.* (2000) have highlighted that population bottleneck of the Argentine ant seems to be associated with a decrease of intraspecific aggression which may permits this insect to form supercolonies. Creation of these supercolonies allowed this ant to quickly invade all the continents except Antarctic. However, not everyone has the

winning ticket of the bottleneck lottery, and it is more probable that bottleneck will negatively affect population survival than the contrary. Nei *et al.* (1975) showed that the loss of genetic diversity is governed by the founder population size and the growth rate of the population. Lower population size or low growth rate will lead to the loss of more alleles, particularly those that are rare (Nei *et al.* 1975, England *et al.* 2003, Willi *et al.* 2006, Dlugosch and Parker 2008). However, rare alleles that persist through a population bottleneck have the opportunity to become common in the new founded population. While many rare alleles are deleterious and under frequency dependent selection those may have important fitness consequences like hatching failure in birds in New Zealand (Briskie and Mackintosh 2004).

While one single introduction event will lead to low genetic diversity, multiple introductions from multiples source populations may increase evolutionary potential and allow for rapid evolution and geographic spread in the new environment. Multiple source-introductions are predicted to increase Mendelian trait diversity in founding populations by raising both population size and population growth rate (Dlugosch and Parker 2008). For the reed canarygrass (*Phalaris arundinacea L.*), multiple introductions of European strains have occurred in North America since the mid-19th century. Lavergne and Molofsky's data showed that introduced samples were issued from disparate European regions, which created the original diverse genetic pattern after introduction. This has resulted in the continental-wide genetic diversity of reed canarygrass in its European range being redistributed and recombined into introduced North American populations (Lavergne and Molofsky 2007). Another example of creation of new genetic diversity in the introduced species is the case of the Cuban lizard, *Anolis sagrei*. Kolbe *et al.* (2004) have showed that eight introductions have occurred in Florida across this lizard's native range, blending genetic variation from different geographic source populations and producing populations that contain substantially more genetic variation than native populations (Kolbe *et al.* 2004). Another example of multiple introduction favouring invasive species is the case of common mynas (*Acridotheres tristis*). In the study of Baker and

Moeed in 1987, this bird introduced to Australia, New Zealand, Fiji, Hawaii, and South Africa during the last century were compared genetically with native populations from India (Baker and Moeed 1987). Authors demonstrated that average heterozygosity, mean number of alleles per locus, and the percentage of polymorphic loci are lower in the introduced populations than in native one. But differences between introduced population and native population are lower in the case of introduction of great number of individuals (e.g. New Zealand) than in the case of introduction of small number of individuals (e.g. South Africa) (Baker and Moeed 1987). This kind of results is the same for some others invasive birds like chaffinch *Fringilla coelebs* and European starling *Sturnus vulgaris* (Blackburn *et al.* 2009). The case of starling is observed between the native population from Great Britain and the multiple introduced populations from New Zealand. An analyse of allozymes polymorphism have highlighted an equivalent level of heterozygosity and proportion of polymorphism between these two locations (Ross 1983). So, in case of multiple introductions, the genetic diversity in alien species is expected to be higher than in case of one introduction event.

In summary, alien invasive species are confront to a paradox that is, how foundering populations that typically have low genetic diversity, low evolutionary potential and perhaps low reproductive fitness can become invasive (Allendorf and Lundquist 2003, Frankham 2005).

c. The use of population genetics

Population genetics aim to investigate genetic structure and population dynamics. Thanks to this discipline we can determine if populations of an invasive species have been subjected to a bottleneck, isolation events or describe its dispersal patterns (Lee 2002, Stepien *et al.* 2002, Astanei *et al.* 2005, Puillandre *et al.* 2008). For example, studying population genetics has permitted us to identify the source population of the pathogenic influenza A H5N1. Wallace *et al.* in 2007 have shown that the Chinese province of Guangdong is the source of multiple H5N1 strains

spreading at both regional and international scales (Wallace *et al.* 2007). The case of the zebra mussel, *Dreissena polymorpha*, a bivalve species native to the Black and Caspian seas, and which has invaded Ireland and North America in the last decade is another example of the application of population genetics. Astanei *et al.* (2005) used microsatellites markers to investigate genetic diversity and population structure in 10 populations across Europe and the Great Lakes in North America. The results suggest that the zebra mussel has been introduced in Ireland and in North America in large numbers of individuals by trade boats.

Different tools are available in the field of population genetics. There are mainly two kinds of genetic tools. The first one is the sequencing of a piece of genome (i.e. mitochondrial, chloroplast or nuclear genome); the second is the use of different copies (i.e. alleles) for specific small region in the genome using markers. Brown in his review in 1996, defined an ideal marker system would be one in which: (a) no band (fragment size) maps to more than one locus; (b) all bands are completely reproducible; (c) all alleles at a locus can be identified; (d) markers are in linkage equilibrium within each sub-population; (e) no marker is selected, linked to a selected gene or is in linkage disequilibrium with a selected gene in any of the sub-populations; (f) most alleles are at intermediate frequencies (Brown 1996). Different nuclear markers would fulfil these conditions, among them are found RFLP (Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism), microsatellites and recently developed SNPs (Single Nucleotide Polymorphic sites).

Due to the maternal inheritance and the lack of recombination of mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA), the mutations accumulated throughout a species history trace the maternal genealogy (Awise 1994, Edwards *et al.* 2005, Zink and Barrowclough 2008). Hence, the variable part of the mtDNA such as the control region allows the genealogy on population level to be captured in a fair amount of detail, as was shown in different species like cattle, chicken or pig to name only a few (Kim *et al.* 2002, Jia *et al.* 2007, Silva *et al.* 2008). But some authors raise the fact that maternally inherited mtDNA can never capture enough of a species history to explain all population

structure and need to be complete by analysing nuclear marker (Edwards *et al.* 2005, Zink and Barrowclough 2008).

Microsatellites are actually the marker of choice for most applications in population genetics and molecular ecology. There is extensive knowledge on general aspects of their use (Selkoe and Toonen 2006), pitfalls (Pompanon *et al.* 2005), development (Zane *et al.* 2002), evolution (Ellegren 2004), and transfer across species (Dawson *et al.* 2010). Several properties make microsatellites attractive for studies of non-model organisms. From a practical point of view, they are relatively easy to develop and can be analyzed at moderate cost. From a conceptual point of view, the unusually high mutation rate of microsatellites renders them particularly useful in context of estimating levels of genomic diversity.

So combination of mitochondrial and nuclear marker will be enough to describe the genetic diversity of an invasive alien species and its population structure.

d. South Africa, a stopover for introduced species

Biological introductions can be intentional and serve agricultural, horticulture, forestry purposes and biological control. Intentional or not, it has been shown that introductions followed human pathway, and are closely linked to humans transport routes (road, maritime transport, etc (Kolar and Lodge 2001)). This is the case for example, of the house mouse (*Mus musculus*) which have follow human since beginning of civilization. This successful settlement must be considered to be a consequence of the development of human sedentism and of systematic cereal harvesting and storage (Tchernov 1984). South Africa, by his history and geographic position, has always been an important destination for European countries for maritime trade, and a compulsory stop in the route to India. In addition, its history as European colony and Commonwealth member has facilitate export/import exchanges with Asia and Europe. During the past three and a half centuries, 8750 different exotic plants have been introduced for the purposes of horticulture, agronomy or forestry (Joubert and Bosch 2009). Most of these stayed in the limits of

their domestication. But some, 180 plants species have become invaders (Joubert and Bosch 2009). It is estimate that about 22.5% of the most widely distributed species are represented by alien plant species in South Africa (Stohlgren *et al.* 2011). Forty-eight alien bird species have also found their way into South Africa's borders, but only four have become invasive (the common starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*), the common myna (*Acridotheres tristis*), the house crow (*Corvus splendens*) and the house sparrow (*Passer domesticus domesticus*)) (Joubert and Bosch 2009). The case of the common starling is very interesting because it was introduced only one time (18 individuals) in Cape Town by the Governor of the Cape, Cecil John Rhodes in 1897 (Harrison *et al.* 1997). The first edition of South African Birds of Roberts in 1940 listed this bird as restricted to Cape Town and 'adjoining districts'. Currently, 1.14 millions of common starlings occupied the southern and eastern coasts and are particularly presents on the region of Cape Town (Cang Hui, pers. communication). This bird is among the 3 worst of the World's Worst Invasive alien Species (Lowe *et al.* 2007). But published literature on its genetic structure is scattered and in South Africa is still unknown.

Based on microsatellites and mitochondrial data, this study aims to assess the relative importance of genetic diversity in the actual invasion process but also to dispersal patterns and spread rate of the common starling in South Africa.

Methods

a. Species studied

The common starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*) is a bird of the *Sturnidae* family in the order of Passeriformes (Fig. 2 and 3). This species of starling is native to temperate Europe and western Asia. It was introduced and is invasive in Australia, New Zealand, North America, and South Africa.

Figure 2: Phylogenetic orders of birds. Phylogenetic tree of all orders of birds displaying the relative evolutionary distance based on an alignment of 32 kb of nuclear DNA which represents 19 nuclear loci (Hackett et al. 2008, Crowley et al. 2009)

Starlings are 19–22 cm long, with a wingspan of 37–42 cm and a weight of 60–90g. Its plumage is shiny black and spangled with white. The breeding season begins in early spring and finish in summer. The eggs (4-5) are small and blue with an incubation period of 13 days. The age of maturity is reach at one year and the record of longevity is 20 years old.

Figure 3: Details of common starling and its eggs

Young starlings disperse in search of food and nest sites; they may move great distances to feed. For example, the spread rate of the starling in Europe is 200km² per year (Hengeveld 1989, Holmes 1993). Cabe (1999) found that the average distance moved by juveniles in the USA was 104 km. This author wrote that just over half of the birds returned to their birth sites to breed. Feare in 1984 highlighted that only 20% of juveniles moving more than 100 kilometres from their birth sites and another 20% from the same colony moved less than ten kilometres (Feare 1984). In contrast to the migratory populations in Europe and North America, starlings in Australia display no large-scale seasonal movements. In fact, in Australia common starlings

used to be sedentary, with an average movement of two kilometres recorded from banding recoveries; however, some long distance movements are also present – up to 987 kilometres (Higgins *et al.* 2006). Dolbeer (1982) found that, 30 % juveniles in North America breed for their first reproductive season further than 50 km, and 12 % further than 200 km. After what, adults usually come back to the same nesting area every reproductive season (from 10 km for females, and 15 for males). Common starlings has the ability to adapt to a large variety of habitats has allowed for their dispersal and establishment throughout the world, resulting in a habitat range from coastal wetlands to alpine forests, from sea level to 1900 meters above sea level (Higgins *et al.* 2006).

The common starling is preferentially insectivorous but sometimes it could be omnivorous and can also eat grains, seeds, fruits, nectars, and garbage if the opportunity arises. This bird species occurs in large numbers and forage on fruit orchards or wheat fields which create an economic loss. Common starlings are aggressive and will compete with native fauna for food. They also frequently take over nest sites from native birds (Weber 1979). In South Africa, common starling is present in the southern parts of the country which is represented by the Western Cape Province and the Eastern Cape Province (Fig. 4).

Figure 4 : Map of distribution of common starling *Sturnus vulgaris* (green spots) in South Africa in 1997

b. Field sampling

Models of landscape influence on genetic variation require continuously distributed sampling within the scale of spatial dependency (Storfer *et al.* 2007). We designed a random sampling to capture the range of variability across landscape variables. Geographic information systems (GIS) were used to identify the variability ranges of several environmental factors. In addition, in order to identify their dispersal pattern such as IBD, it is recommended to estimate relatedness between samples that are distant at σ to 50σ (with σ^2 the average squared axial parent-offspring distance defined by Rousset (2000)) (Leblois *et al.* 2000, Vekemans and Hardy 2004). This approach allows us to identify 40 sampling locations in South Africa with 235 samples, taken from across the distribution of starlings in the country (Fig. 5). All samples were taken during the reproductive season, season at which dispersal is the lowest and allows to assume that the birds belongs to the locality it has been sampled. For comparisons we have included some individuals from England (16 birds) and from Namibia, the neighbouring country to South Africa (10 individuals).

Figure 5: Map of distribution of starlings (black spot) sampling for the study and their distribution across the country (grey spot)

c. DNA methods

In total, DNA was extracted from 261 individuals using DNeasy Blood & Tissue QIAGEN® kit according to manufacturer's instructions with and incubation at 56°C over night.

We have selected microsatellite loci designed for passerine species in the literature (Otter *et al.* 1998, Dawson *et al.* 2000, Richardson *et al.* 2000, Rubenstein 2005, Celis *et al.* 2007). Each of these was blasted against the zebra finch (*Taeniopygia guttata*) genome in order to identify potential chromosome location and select markers that are widely distributed.

Table 1: Microsatellites primers and theirs characteristics

Primer	Amount	Reference	Multiplex	Na	Primer sequence (5'-3')
Ase19	2,2µL	Richardson <i>et al.</i> 2000	3	6	<i>F: TAGGGTCCCAGGGAGGAAG</i> <i>R: TCTGCCCATTAGGGAAAAGTC</i>
Patmp2-43	1µL	Otter <i>et al.</i> 1998	1	2	<i>F: ACAGGTAGTCAGAAATGGAAAG</i> <i>R: GTATCCAGAGTCTTTGCTGATG</i>
Pcapµ3	2µL	Dawson <i>et al.</i> 2000	1	5	<i>F: GGTGTTTGTGAGCCGGGG</i> <i>R: TGTTACAACCAAAGCGGTCATTTG</i>
SS1-6	2µL	Rubenstein 2005	2	6	<i>F: TTTCAGTGGCTGGATCTGGTAAACC</i> <i>R: CTAGCAACATATAGCCCAAGCTGTATTGAT</i>
SS2-106	3µL	Rubenstein 2005	1	6	<i>F: TGTGTTATCCCATTGTAAGGGCTCTTT</i> <i>R: GACTCTAGGTGGAAACCCCATTTT</i>
SS2-119	1,5µL	Rubenstein 2005	1	6	<i>F: CGGTTAAGTATGCAATGCACCTTTTG</i> <i>R: GCCCTGTCCCAACCCCTCAT</i>
SS2-130	1,5µL	Rubenstein 2005	3	6	<i>F: CTGAAGGCACCCAGCAGGTTCT</i> <i>R: AGACCCACTGTGATAATTACCACCTTCTCTG</i>
SS2-16	2,5µL	Rubenstein 2005	3	7	<i>F: CTGTATTGCCACCTTCCCTTGTAGTTC</i> <i>R: TTAGGTGGCTTTTCTGAGCAGGTTATGT</i>
SS2-32	2,5µL	Rubenstein 2005	3	13	<i>F: GGTATCACCATATCTGCTGCCAGT</i> <i>R: CAGGCTTTTGTGACAATTATTTTG</i>
SS2-68	2,2µL	Rubenstein 2005	2	2	<i>F: AACTTGCTGGTTGAAAATTTTAATG</i> <i>R: TGTCTTTAATTGTTACTCAGAAAGTGAA</i>
SS2-71B	1,5µL	Rubenstein 2005	1	8	<i>F: CACACCCAACATGTAACAAATCTTACA</i> <i>R: CTTTGAGCCTCTGCTTTTAGAAAATTG</i>
SS2-80	1,5µL	Rubenstein 2005	2	2	<i>F: ACCCACTTTTACCTACCTAGCATGTTCTGT</i> <i>R: ATTAGAGTGCCCAAGGACTTGTTCTCA</i>
SS3-42C	2µL	Rubenstein 2005	2	13	<i>F: TATATCCCAGGGAGGGTTGTGGTGTG</i> <i>R: ATCAAACCTGCAGCAGGACTCTGACTGTG</i>
Sta213	1,5µL	Celis <i>et al.</i> 2006	1	15	<i>F: TTGGCCTTGCTGAACTTCTT</i> <i>R: GATCAAGTGCACCTTCAGCA</i>
Sta269	2µL	Celis <i>et al.</i> 2006	2	8	<i>F: TGGGGATTAATAGGGGTGTG</i> <i>R: GCAGTGAGAAGAGGGCTTTG</i>
Sta294	2µL	Celis <i>et al.</i> 2006	2	7	<i>F: AGGAACATGGCTGGAGTGAA</i> <i>R: CACAGTCACATTGGCATTGA</i>
Sta308	2µL	Celis <i>et al.</i> 2006	3	17	<i>F: GCTTAAGCACCCCTCACAAAC</i> <i>R: CTGCAATCAGGGTTTGATT</i>

All of these markers have been organized in three multiplexes (Table 1). A QIAGEN® Multiplex Kit was used to the recommended volume with each primer at a concentration of 10pmole/µL. We used a polymerase chain reaction (PCR) programme consisting of 35 cycles each at the following annealing temperatures: 94°C, 62°C, 72°C for multiplex 1 and consisting of 35 cycles each at the following

annealing temperatures: 94°C, 59°C, 72°C for multiplex 2 and 3. Samples were genotyped using GLZ-500 (Liz) in each capillary as a size standard. Allele sizes were estimated on GeneMapper® version 3.7 (Applied Biosystems) with a double blind lecture to confirm genotypes found.

Mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) were sequenced using a QIAGEN® Multiplex Kit with 5µL of QIAGEN kit, 1µL of DNA at 50ng/µL and 1µL of each primer at a concentration of 10 pmole/µL. We used two primers designed for amplified the control region of mtDNA (Table 2): svCRL1 and svPhe3 to amplified a segment of about 1200pb (Rollins *et al.* 2011). Because sequences quality decreased after 700-800 pb and instead of two-ways sequencing we used a third primer svCRL2 situated 250 pb downstream. Therefore, two sequences per samples were obtained: one from svCRL1 from 0-800pb and one from svCRL2 from 250-1000 pb. This approach was preferred because 1) there are multiples repeat at the end of the sequence that do not successfully allowed a reverse-sequencing and 2) haplotypes from Rollins *et al.* (2011) showed that no polymorphism was found at the very end of the sequence leading to high confidence in the peaks observed at the end of the sequence. A PCR programme consisting of 45 cycles each at the following annealing temperatures: 94°C, 55.5°C, 72°C was performed. Samples were sequenced by MACROGEN in South Korea.

Table 2: Mitochondrial DNA Control primers

Primer	Reference	Primer sequence (5'-3')
svCRL1	Rollins <i>et al.</i> 2011	<i>F: ACTTTTCTCGTGCTTAAAGGGAT</i>
svCRL2	Rollins <i>et al.</i> 2011	<i>F: AGAGACATTCTTGTTTCAGGTAC</i>
svPhe3	Rollins <i>et al.</i> 2011	<i>R:GCCGTCTTGACATCTTCAGT</i>

d. Statistical analyses

Genetic diversity

The first step of statistical analyses is the verification of the data on hand. The presence of null alleles was checked with the software FreeNA with 10 000 replicates (Chapuis and Estoup 2007). Microsatellite data were verified for departures from Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium, linkage disequilibrium and F_{st} with Genepop version 4.1 (Rousset 2008) with a Bonferroni correction. Data have been converted from text format to Genetix, Fstat and Genepop file using Convert 1.31 (Glaubitz 2004). Next we used GENALEX 6.41 (Peakall and Smouse 2006), GENETIX 4.05 (Belkhir *et al.* 1996-2004) and Fstat 2.9.3 (Goudet 2001) for calculate the total number of alleles, the number of private alleles, effective allele number, allele frequencies and heterozygoty. The observed number of alleles in a sample is highly dependent on sample size, consequently allelic richness was calculated using a rarefaction index advised by El Mousadik and Petit, and implemented in Fstat 2.9.3 (El Mousadik and Petit 1996, Goudet 2001).

In order to estimate genetic structure similarity across loci and measure the contribution of each specific marker we used a multivariate co-inertia analysis (MCoA) (Laloë *et al.* 2007, Berthouly *et al.* 2008). This analysis permit to compare each separate typology obtained from each marker, to the reference typology. It highlights three important parameters: 1) the variance of genetic diversity within a locus, 2) the similarity (Cos^2) which shows the correlation between scores of individual locus table and the synthetic variable of the same rank, and 3) the typological value which is the contribution of markers to the reference typology. This analysis was performed with ADE4 package (Chessel *et al.* 2004, Dray *et al.* 2007) on R 2.13.0 software (R Development Core Team 2011).

Isolation by distance (IBD)

IBD over South Africa was assessed by testing the correlation between genetic and geographical distance considering all individuals pairs. This analysis was performed with 10 000 permutations between individuals, 10 000 permutations across loci and 10 000 permutations between locations on the population of common starling of South Africa on the software Spagedi 1.3 (Hardy and Vekemans 2002). Geographical distances, have been considered like straight-line distances between all pairs of birds.

We used the distance measure \hat{a} from Rousset (2000) as statistic index of pairwise genetic differentiation. We also tested the kinship measure described in Loiselle *et al.* (Loiselle *et al.* 1995) because Vekemans and Hardy (2004) have showed that it can be more accurate.

When an isolation by distance pattern is representative of the genetic structure of the population, the dispersal parameters is expected to be equal to $1/4\pi D\sigma^2$ in two-dimensional space with D the effective density and σ^2 the mean average squared of parent-offspring distance (Rousset 2000). As σ is unknown, an iterative approach can be applied, assuming that the effective density, D , is known (Heuertz *et al.* 2003). Therefore, a first estimate of $D\sigma^2$ is based on a global regression, then $\hat{\sigma}$ (i.e. estimation of σ); is extracted, and a new estimate of $D\sigma^2$ is based on a restricted regression considering only pairs separated by a distance between $\hat{\sigma}$ and $50\hat{\sigma}$. The process is repeated until successive $\hat{\sigma}$ estimates are stabilized (procedure implemented in the software SPAGeDi; Hardy and Vekemans 2002). The estimated density d of starling in South Africa is 3.74 per km². We did not have an estimation the effective population size which would allows to estimate the effective density. Therefore we calculate distances considering from $D=0.25d$ to $0.75d$.

Population Structure

For determination of population structure in first step we performed Bayesian clustering analyses to infer spatial structure in the genetic data. Several methods are currently available that implement this general type of analysis, and alternative methods sometimes show different results (Latch *et al.* 2006). We employed the most widely used approach, which is implemented in STRUCTURE version 2.3.3 (Pritchard *et al.* 2000, Falush *et al.* 2003), and likewise utilized a second approach as implemented in GENELAND version 3.3.0 (Guillot *et al.* 2005).

STRUCTURE software is powerful in inferring the number of clusters in a population but F_{ST} must be at least 0.05 to reach an assignment accuracy of greater than 97% (Latch *et al.* 2006). This is not our case, so we used the LocPrior model implemented in STRUCTURE which is not only based on the individual genotypes but also takes into account the sampling locations to differentiate potential sub-population across South Africa (Hubisz *et al.* 2009). This approach is recommended by authors when the signal of structure is relatively weak (Pritchard *et al.* 2000, Hubisz *et al.* 2009). We conducted five independent runs for each value of K ranging from 1 to 40. We used the admixture model to analyse English, Namibian and South African population and added sampling locations as prior information when studying the South African population alone. We also assumed correlated allele frequencies among populations (Falush *et al.* 2003). Each run consisted in 250 000 burn-in steps followed by 100 000 iterations. To determinate the most likely number of clusters we used the $Pr(K)$ of Pritchard *et al.* (2000) and Evanno *et al.* (2005). Evanno's approach automatically discard the possibility of $K=1$, therefore is it first necessary to check for $K=1$ following Pritchard *et al.* (2000). ΔK from Evanno *et al.* was estimated using Structure Harvester software (Pritchard *et al.* 2010, Earl 2011).

To assess results from STRUCTURE analysis, with also used GENELAND software (Guillot *et al.* 2005, Guillot *et al.* 2011). In our GENELAND analyses, we performed a

series of runs to infer the number of genetic groups (K) in our data. We used the correlated allele frequencies option. K was inferred as the number of genetic groups estimated among 10 runs of 350 000 iterations.

Finally to assess all previous results, we also performed a spatial Principal Component Analysis (sPCA) implemented in the *adegenet* package (Jombart 2008, Jombart *et al.* 2008) of R 2.13.0 (R Development Core Team 2011). The spatial principal component analysis is a tool to investigate cryptic spatial patterns of genetic variability using geo-referenced multilocus genotypes. This method relies on a modification of PCA in taking into account the variance between the studied entities (individuals or populations) and also their spatial autocorrelation. First, the spatial information is modelled through a connection network which is, secondly, used to calculate the Moran's *I* index of spatial autocorrelation. This index is incorporated in the sPCA criterion and permit to identified global and local pattern in allelic frequency data. Global pattern indicates an increase in differentiation with geographic distances, while local pattern indicates geographically closed individuals are more genetically different than distant individuals.

Mitochondrial DNA analyses

The mtDNA chromatographs were read and assessed using DNA baser version 3 (Heracle-Software). Contigs for each of the control region sequences were edited with BioEdit software (Hall 1999) and aligned with the CLUSTAL W package implemented in BioEdit (Thompson *et al.* 1994). The alignment obtained (240 sequences) is 924pb length including sequences from Australian and English starlings from the study of Rollins *et al.* (2011) available on Genbank (Accession No. FJ542126 to FJ542146 and Accession No. HQ263623 to HQ263642). An outgroup of mitochondrial sequences from *Sturnus sericeus* (Accession No. HM859900), *Sturnus cineraceus* (Accession No. HQ896037), *Acridotheres cristatellus* (Accession No. JF810423) and *Acridotheres tristis* (Accession No. HQ915864) found on GenBank

were added to the further analyses. Polymorphisms segments was analyzed using MEGA5 (Tamura *et al.* 2011).

First step in analyses of mtDNA is determining the evolutionary model which characterizes genomic region. This analyse was performed with jModelTest software (Posada 2008). Secondly, we built a tree with haplotype using PhyML software (Guindon and Gascuel 2003) with 100 bootstrap and using the TPM2uf model (Kimura 1981). Haplotype diversity (θ_{π}) was estimated using the ARLEQUIN 3.5 package (Excoffier and Lischer 2010).

Results

a. Microsatellites

Genetic diversity

Data relative to polymorphism of each locus are presented in Table 3. Among the 17 microsatellites loci, none of them show r value above 0.2 so we can considered that there is no null allele present in these data. We detected in total 127 alleles among these 17 loci (Table 3). The number of alleles per locus ranged from 2 (Pamtp2-43, SS2-68 and SS2-80) to 15 (Sta213 and Sta308), with a mean number of 7.5 per locus. The observed heterozygosity (H_{OBS}) per locus averaged 0.616 and ranged from 0.267 for locus SS2-80 to 0.920 for locus Sta308.

Table 3: Genetic diversity among loci

<i>Loci</i>	<i>No A</i>	<i>Allele range</i>	H_{EXP}	H_{OBS}	F_{IS}	F_{ST}	D_{HWE}
Ase 19	6	156-175	0,493±0,109	0,424±0,063	0,118	0,047	0
Patmp2-43	2	124-126	0,440±0,039	0,392±0,032	0,081	0,021	0
Pcau3	5	172-182	0,719±0,030	0,674±0,069	0,035	0,022	0
SS1-6	6	195-213	0,740±0,040	0,736±0,064	-0,025	0,031	0
SS2-106	6	273-288	0,687±0,046	0,541±0,041	0,189	0,037	1
SS2-119	6	274-286	0,530±0,046	0,567±0,033	-0,098	0,031	0
SS2-130	6	245-255	0,511±0,094	0,526±0,085	-0,056	0,062	0
SS2-16	7	193-207	0,713±0,059	0,748±0,052	-0,078	0,035	0
SS2-32	13	228-254	0,858±0,014	0,750±0,111	0,101	0,059	0
SS2-68	2	138-140	0,472±0,016	0,401±0,039	0,127	0,075	0
SS2-71B	8	311-332	0,725±0,031	0,716±0,052	-0,016	0,015	0
SS2-80	2	306-312	0,315±0,086	0,267±0,038	0,127	0,078	0
SS3-42C	13	133-161	0,814±0,018	0,835±0,050	-0,055	0,028	1
Sta 213	15	146-193	0,821±0,043	0,662±0,081	0,171	0,037	1
Sta 269	8	180-203	0,767±0,032	0,773±0,065	-0,037	0,032	0
Sta 294	7	292-305	0,639±0,024	0,544±0,029	0,125	0,023	0
Sta 308	15	120-158	0,904±0,016	0,920±0,041	-0,048	0,032	0

No A: number of alleles; H_{EXP} , unbiased expected heterozygosity; H_{OBS} , observed heterozygosity; F_{IS} & F_{ST} , F-statistics; D_{HWE} , number of populations in heterozygote deficiency

The multiple co-inertia analysis (MCoA) is dedicated to assess the choice of marker. In results of this analysis the markers of interest should be both highly variable and congruent in order to perform a consensus typology. In our case, the

variation across loci (first graph Fig. 7) fluctuated and showed that there is enough variation to adequately describe the population. Similarity values exhibited high Cos^2 between 0.802 and 1 and only the locus SS2-119 had low Cos^2 value of 0.214 (second graph on Fig. 6). Thus, Cos^2 value showed a congruence of genetic structure for the population of starling across 16 loci. Diagram of typological values (last graph on Fig. 6) indicated that the maximum percentage (12.3%) is reached by SS2-32 and the lower percentage is attained by loci SS2-106 and SS2-119 (respectively 0.31% and 0.63%). The typological value varied among markers which indicate that some markers are more efficient in discriminating the genetic pattern. So in conclusion we have here at least 15 makers with a discriminatory power.

Figure 6: Distribution across loci of values for the components to first axis, in percentages: Variance, Similarity (Cos^2), Typological Value

The mean number of alleles per locus found per country varied from 4.35 to 6.94 (Table 4). Allelic richness, again per country, averaged over loci ranged from

4.35 to 5.53. Populations of starlings from England had 9 private alleles compared with 14 for the South African's population and none for Namibia. Starlings from England showed the higher rate of observed heterozygosity and number of effective alleles (0.622; 3.98 respectively) compare to Namibia (0.624; 3.00) and South Africa (0.603; 3.73). There was no evidence of linkage between loci, which were then considered statistically independent. Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium was tested for each locus in each population and no significant evidence of departure from Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium was found.

Table 4: Genetic diversity among population

<i>Population</i>	N_i	H_{EXP}	H_{OBS}	A	A_e	D_{HWE}	R	N_a	<i>Private allele</i>
England	16	0,698±0,040	0,622±0,047	106	3,98	0	5,53	6,23	9
Namibia	10	0,618±0,051	0,624±0,057	74	3,00	0	4,35	4,35	0
South Africa	235	0,652±0,040	0,603±0,038	118	3,73	3	4,88	6,94	14

N_i , number of animals genotyped; H_{EXP} , unbiased expected heterozygosity; H_{OBS} , observed heterozygosity; A , number of alleles; A_e , number of effective alleles; D_{HWE} , number of loci in heterozygote deficiency; R , allelic richness; N_a , mean number of alleles per population.

The pairwise genetic differentiation (F_{ST}) is equal to 0.036 between the English population and the Namibian one (Table 5). Between South Africa and England differentiation as measured by F_{ST} is equal to 0.032 and finally differentiation between Namibia and South Africa is 0.006. A significant difference was found between native population (England) and introduced populations (South Africa-Namibia). No evidence of significant differentiation was highlighted between the Southern African populations.

Table 5: Genetic differentiation (F_{ST}) between populations of common starling

F_{ST}	<i>South Africa</i>	<i>England</i>
<i>England</i>	0.032*	-
<i>Namibia</i>	0.006	0.036*

Within the South African population, observed heterozygosity ranged from 0.494 to 0.765. Plotting the observed heterozygosity on a map of South Africa (Fig. 6) shows that we have some “hot-spots” of heterozygosity localised on the edge of the sampling area (dark-red filled circles) and low rate heterozygosity appear scattered (open circles). The average of F_{IS} across South African population is 0.072 which indicate a deficit of heterozygosity in this population. No significant differentiation between localities has been found.

Figure 7: Map of distribution of observed heterozygosity across the localities in South Africa with low rate of heterozygosity = 0.494 to 0.567; medium = 0.567 to 0.637; high = 0.637 to 0.765

Population structure

When running STRUCTURE with the samples from the three on the 3 countries data set, we were able to discriminate English population from the African ones (Fig. 8).

Figure 8: Clustering results for all populations sampled (for $K = 2$). Each individual is represented as a vertical line portioned into K coloured segments, whose length is proportional to the individual's estimated membership coefficients in the 2 clusters. Individuals of different populations are separated by a black line. Populations are labelled below and on the top of the figure

No differentiation between Namibian and South African populations was found. We then run STRUCTURE within the South African population. Using Pritchard *et al.* (2001) approach we found $K=1$. However, we checked for the $K=2$ pattern found with the Evannos' method (Fig. 9).

Figure 9: Figure 8: Graphic of ΔK from Evannos' method and table of index calculate from Pritchard *et al.* (2010)

For $K=2$, we found that q values were closed to 0.5 at the middle of the sampling area, increasing and reaching 0.9/0.1 at the edges of the sampling (Fig. 10).

Figure 10: Map of the admixture q value in South African population of starling

In 45% of iterations, GENELAND identified 2 clusters, while in the remaining 55% K values ranged from 1 to 40. In addition, no consistency of individuals' assignment was observed. Therefore, even with the spatial information we can't identify any sub-population of starlings in South Africa.

Previous Bayesian analyses assumed that populations are at Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium and in panmixia. Such assumptions are not made for principal component analysis which can therefore be more appropriate. Using spatial Principal Component Analysis (sPCA), we found that the three first global eigen values were significant, and thus indicate a spatial structure at a large scale, in other words geographically distant individuals are more genetically different than geographically close individual. The starling scores on the first principal axis are plotted onto the map of South Africa (Fig. 11). The first axis greatly differentiates the extremes of the sampling distribution.

Figure 11: Map of the score of individuals on the first axis of the sPCA analysis

In fact with an origin of Cape Town, birds became more and more genetically differentiate with a progression to the East. The regression on starlings sPCA values against longitude coordinates (Fig. 12) show a significant slope (Student test shows a *p-value* inferior to 0.001) and a R^2 of 0.58. Such results indicate an IBD pattern on the invasive population of starling in South Africa.

Figure 12: Score of individuals on the first axis of sPCA against the X coordinates (longitude)

Isolation by distance (IBD)

Results from SPAGeDi show that the genetic differentiation between individuals' pairs increased significantly with geographical distance among population of South Africa with a slope of 0.0024 (Fig. 13).

Figure 13: Regression of pairwise genetic distance against the logarithm (ln) of the geographical distance.

When $D=0.25d$ and a 2-dimension dispersal; parent-offspring distance ranged from 9.2 to 10 km with an average at 9.7 km. When $D= 0.75d$; parent-offspring distance ranged from 2.74 to 8 km with an average at 4.15 km.

b. Mitochondrial DNA

The 924pb alignment contained 35 variables sites which characterized 43 haplotypes plus 4 from the outgroup (Table 6). There are 8 private haplotypes in South Africa, 17 in England and 11 in Australia. There is no private haplotype in Namibia. The haplotype diversity (Θ_{π}) is greater in England (5.31) and Australia (5.69) than in Africa. The Namibian population showed the lower rate of haplotype diversity (1.67 differences). In each population the number of transition is higher than the number of transversion which is in coherence with the fact that transitions

are less likely to result in amino acid substitutions, and are therefore more likely to persist as silent substitutions in populations.

Table 6: Characteristics of the 924pb sequences: number of haplotypes, private haplotypes, transition, transversion, private substitution sites and haplotype diversity (Θ_π) of starling populations from England, South Africa, Namibia and Australia

<i>Molecular diversity indexes</i>	<i>England</i>	<i>South Africa</i>	<i>Namibia</i>	<i>Australia</i>
Number of sequences	27	186	10	17
Number of haplotypes	21	14	2	16
Number of private haplotypes	17	8	0	11
Number of transitions	24	12	3	17
Number of transversions	1	1	0	1
No. private substitution sites	12	3	0	9
$\Theta_\pi \pm$ S.D.	5.34 \pm 2.96	4.22 \pm 2.33	1.68 \pm 1.21	5.72 \pm 3.22

The 43 haplotypes from *Sturnus vulgaris* were characterized by only 20 parsimony-informative sites. Unfortunately, the tree based on haplotypes is not consistent possibly due to a lack of information in sequences. The value of bootstrap varying between 0.3% and 84% with the majority around 10%. The only consistent branches (i.e. branches found with a value of bootstrap superior to 50%) are between species of outgroup, between the outgroup and our data and also between haplotypes A6-A7, C1-C2, C2-C3, H1-H3, K1-K2, K2-K3 and J1-J2.

A bootstrap 50% majority-rule consensus tree was draw (Fig. 14) to represent the relations between haploypes obtained in at least 50% of trees tested.

Figure 14: Bootstrap 50% majority-rule consensus tree obtain from mtDNA data (Blue: South African haplotypes, Green: England, Red: Australia, Yellow: Namibia; Pink: outgroup)

Taking into account haplotypes present in at least two continents (J3, I2, K3, I4, D1, A1,) and a common ancestor for clustered branches (J1-J2, K1-K2) we can at least assumed 7 ancestor haplotypes. Mapping the South African haplotypes (Fig.15) permit to identify the three majors haplotypes: K3, I2 and F1 (respectively red, blue and yellow and the map). In fact we can see all of them across the distribution area. This map permitted to identify that haplotype diversity is higher in the region of Cape Town.

Figure 15: Map of repartition of haplotype in South Africa

In contrary, some haplotypes seems to be localized such as haplotypes A8 and J1 (respectively pink and light green in Fig. 15). They are only present around Cape Town and at the edge of the sampling area. This could be explained by the fact that we have some birds which dispersed on great distance.

Discussion

a. South African starling invasion

To efficiently combat invasive species we need to know their history including introduction to actual invasion. For the common starling in South Africa, we have fitted several pieces of the puzzle regarding its invasive history using data derived from mitochondrial and nuclear markers. The birds arrived from England and were introduced into the port of Cape Town. This is confirmed by the high levels of heterozygosity and haplotype diversity observed in and around Cape Town. Concerning the number of introductions, South African starlings show less heterozygosity than native, it seems more probable that only one introduction occurred even if we cannot exclude various introductions from genetically closed individuals/subpopulations. In the case of multiple introductions from divergent subpopulations, we would expect to see a rate of genetic diversity similar or higher than in the native population (Dlugosch and Parker 2008). Following the initial introduction into Cape Town, starlings established and became invasive.

b. Founding population

The genetic data differentiates the native population (English starlings) from introduced populations (South Africa and Namibia). This result could be explained by the founder effect that occurred more than 100 years ago and the absence of gene flow between continents. The similar number of private alleles found in South Africa and England may be because relatively few birds were included from England; the prediction would be that as the sample size for England increases, the number of unique (private) haplotypes / alleles in South Africa would decrease. However the founder effect is present but difference between native population and introduced population is low with only a difference of 0.04 for the rate of heterozygosity and 1.6 for the allelic richness. In other exotic invasive species as the house sparrow (*Passer domesticus*) the difference between native and introduced population is greater with

for example a difference of 0.12 for the rate of heterozygosity and 3.8 for allelic richness (Schrey *et al.* 2011). Even the F_{IS} (i.e. inbreeding coefficient) is lower in introduced populations of starling (0.046 in Namibia and 0.072 in South Africa) than in introduced populations of house sparrow (0.19). This highlighted the fact that starling stays well diversified even after a strong founder effect. Considering the fact that only one introduction has supposedly occurred.

The consensus tree obtained from analysis of mitochondrial data highlight the fact that we don't have enough information in our alignment to really compare the haplotypes and their origins. But as we can observe on the tree some haplotypes are shared between Australia, England, South Africa and Namibia. Knowing that no exchange of starling have occurred between Australia and South Africa and the unique common point is England, we can assess that these shared haplotypes have an English origin. However more informations could be obtained by including longer stretches of sequence data. Lovette *et al.* have sequenced some mitochondrial genes (NDII, COI, COII, ATPase8, and ATPase6) and nuclear introns (rhodopsin intron 1, intron 5 of transforming growth factor β -2 intron 5, and the closely linked β -fibrinogen introns 5 and 7) to reconstruct the phylogeny of Sturnidae (Lovette and Rubenstein 2007, Lovette *et al.* 2008). Other study on genetic differentiation and plumage evolution within the population of pied flycatcher (order of Passeriformes) have used few mtDNA sequences (NADH dehydrogenase subunit 6 gene, and the control region) (Haavie *et al.* 2000). In regards to these studies, we can probably improve our mitochondrial data in sequencing other genes as COI or NADH on mtDNA and β -fibrinogen in the nuclear genome.

c. Pattern of dispersion

Starlings seem to follow an isolation by distance pattern. But few points need to be discussed. The first one is the fact that Leblois *et al.* (2004) have demonstrated that IBD is overestimated in the case of density increase in the recent past. The common starling are known to have increased in density during the last 60 years (Hui *et al.*

2011), so our data could potentially overestimate the presence of IBD pattern (Leblois *et al.* 2004). This means that we have the possibility to have false positive results.

We have estimated the parent-offspring distance dispersal at 2.74 and 10km/yr. These values are in agreement with the range expansion estimated from historical records (Hui *et al.* 2011). Until 1940 the rate of range expansion is about 6.1km/yr and after 1940 it increases to 25.7 km/yr.

The last important critical point concerning the pattern of dispersion is that usually the IBD pattern is characterized by short distance dispersal and a depletion of genetic diversity in peripheral populations in comparison with higher genetic diversity in core populations. But in our case, high rates of heterozygosity was observed everywhere across the sampling area including in the peripheral population. These results may be explained by the long distance dispersal which disturbed the short distance dispersal characteristic of an IBD pattern. In fact in one hand we have some haplotypes well distributed across the sampling area which could confirm the short distance dispersal pattern. On the other hand few haplotypes are localized, for example haplotypes A8 and J1 (respectively pink and light green in Fig. 13) are present around Cape Town and in the edge of the sampling area. This would suggest that some individuals would disperse for longer distances.

The fact that at the edge of the sampling area there are some birds with a high genetic diversity probably means that we have in the peripheral population some birds with a high capacity of adaptation.

Unfortunately, the fact that there is long distance dispersal birds associated with a high rate of heterozygosity at the range of its distribution, would suggest that the invasion of common starling in South Africa is not over. We are actually in presence of a population in expansion.

Conclusion

In conclusion we found a decrease of genetic diversity but less than expected taking into account the fact that only 20 birds are assumed to have been introduced in South Africa. The common starling shows a genetic pattern of isolation by distance associate with long distance dispersal. This association could explain the presence of peripheral population with a high rate of heterozygosity and may permit to say that the population of starlings is still in expansion.

Further analysis will be focused on the dispersal aspect of invasion of starling. Firstly some tests will be performed to assess the expansion of the population (Fu test, Tajima test and mismatch test). Found the number of founder of the starlings' population is important for developing biologically based management practices, predicting the invasive potential of this species, and making inferences about ecological and evolutionary processes. Next step to analyse the invasive population of starling will be to highlight the dispersal pathways. What kind of way of migration (i.e. roads, coast, bush etc) do these birds selected? Do we have male as long distance disperser and female as short distance dispersal or *vice versa* or no difference exist?

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